

DELIVERABLE D7.1
COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION PLAN

eGROUND WATER

Citizen science and ICT-based enhanced information systems for groundwater assessment, modelling and sustainable participatory management (GA n. 1921).

DELIVERABLE D1.1	COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION PLAN
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Abstract	<p>This document describes the target audiences at which eGROUNDWATER's communication and dissemination will aim, and the means that the project will use. Audiences include large and small farmer associations, river basin authorities, tourism and golf sectors, scientific community and general public. The means to be used will depend on the type of activity (communication or dissemination). A list of targets per audience is included. Dissemination activities of the project's results will be performed using scientific journals, conferences, and workshops and meetings. Communication will rely on social networks, webpages, newsletters and traditional means. Finally, the Communication and Dissemination Unit, responsible of monitoring the development of the communication and dissemination campaigns, is presented.</p>

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

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Executive summary

This document describes the actions executed for Task 7.1. The goal of Task 7.1 is to design a plan to ensure adequate communication and dissemination activities required for the outreach and visibility of eGROUNDWATER and to attract the attention of potential stakeholders. Target groups have been identified and described, and communication and dissemination actions have been designed for each group according to their specific requirements and needs.

The Communication and Dissemination Plan will be coordinated and monitored by the Communication and Dissemination Unit, as described in Section 4 of this document. The outcome of the activities developed in the frame of this plan will be reported annually at D7.3 “Annual report on communication and dissemination activities”.

1 Introduction

Communication and dissemination are core activities of eGROUNDWATER due to the following reasons:

- The project relies on the active involvement of users in the measurement of groundwater variables through citizen science. It is therefore crucial to find out, get in contact with and engage users in the project and its activities, not only as mere followers of the project and its results, but also as data collectors and knowledge co-creators
- The case studies of eGROUNDWATER, as well as the Mediterranean area, refer to diverse geographical, cultural and socio-economic contexts, including the use of different languages. Understanding the particular context of each one is key towards maximizing the involvement of users in the project.

Consequently, eGROUNDWATER needs the development of strong and coordinated dissemination and communication campaigns, properly identifying target audiences and developing tailored activities to maximize its impacts. This deliverable sets up the strategy to develop and coordinate these campaigns. The annual reports on dissemination and communication activities following the guidelines presented in this deliverable will be reported in D7.3.

2 Target audiences

eGROUNDWATER has identified six target audiences to which disseminate and communicate the project and its results. They include relevant users, managers and other stakeholders from the case studies and beyond.

2.1 Large farmer associations

This target audience includes established user unions, irrigation associations and cooperatives gathering a significant number of single users, as well as farmer associations embedding smaller farmer associations. The distinct factor of these farmer associations is that they can play a significant influence on the aquifer abstractions by themselves due to their size and capacity. In case of the large farmer associations present in eGROUNDWATER case studies, their involvement in the project will be sought from the beginning (Taks 3.1), and direct communication channels with them (e.g. phone, e-mail, social networks) will be maintained during the project.

The communication and dissemination objective for this audience is to transmit them how the Enhanced Information System (EIS) developed by eGROUNDWATER can assist them in achieving efficient and sustainable management practices (e.g. saving water by monitoring soil moisture and performing demand-based irrigation practices rather than irrigating the fields with a fixed scheme), as well as in their internal management and procedures (e.g. facilitate their internal accounting and communication, enable the implementation of internal enforcing systems).

A list of large farmer associations at which eGROUNDWATER will aim is shown in Table 1. This list will be updated at each annual report (D7.3). Consortium partners are already in contact with relevant farmer associations in PRIMA regions. For instance, VisualNacert has a widespread portfolio of contacts with large farming companies, especially in Spain, France and North Africa. We will invite their representatives to joint training sessions. Joint training sessions and workshops (Tasks 6.2 and 6.3) will help to demonstrate eGROUNDWATER potential to a variety of users.

Table 1. Large farmer associations to which eGROUNDWATER targets

NAME	APPR. SIZE	AQUIFER	COUNTRY	EXISTING CONTACT	CHANNEL	LANGUAGE	PARTNER(S) IN CHARGE
Riegos del Alto Magro	4.243 ha (1600 users together with Riegos Mixtos de la Plana de Utiel)	Requena-Utiel	Spain	Yes	Phone, email, face-to-face	Spanish	UPV
Riegos mixtos de la Plana de Utiel	1.458 ha (1600 users together with Riegos Mixtos de la Plana de Utiel)	Requena-Utiel	Spain	Yes	Phone, email, face-to-face	Spanish	UPV
Junta Central de Regantes de la Mancha Oriental	10.000 users (88.884 ha)	Mancha Oriental	Spain	Yes	Phone, email, face-to-face	Spanish	UPV
COPAG	21000 approx.	Souss Massa	Morocco	Yes	email	French	Cirad, UMI
Association des foggaras de la wilaya d'Adrar	About 650 foggaras and 12 000 ha	Intercalary Continental (CI)	Algeria	Yes	Phone, email, face-to-face	Arabic	UADA - CIRAD
Madrefruta	NA	Campina de Faro	Portugal	Not yet	-	Portuguese	ISEG/UALG
Algarorange	NA	Campina de Faro	Portugal	Not yet	-	Portuguese	ISEG/UALG
Frusual	100 users (1500 ha)	Campina de Faro	Portugal	Not yet	-	Portuguese	ISEG/UALG
Cacial	94 users (800 ha)	Campina de Faro	Portugal	Not yet	-	Portuguese	ISEG/UALG

2.2 Water agencies

This target audience refers to the River Basin Agencies (RBAs) or equivalent agencies that are responsible of monitoring the quantitative and qualitative status of aquifers and, if necessary, of applying corrective measures to guarantee their long-term sustainability. eGROUNDWATER's EIS will incorporate data from them, since these entities maintain the official groundwater recording networks.

The communication and dissemination objective for this audience is the value brought by the EIS on aquifer monitoring, since more and better information would result imply more accurate assessments on the aquifers' status and more efficient corrective measures if needed. Direct communication with the water agencies related to eGROUNDWATER case studies will be maintained during the project due to their status of traditional data providers.

A list of water authority agencies at which eGROUNDWATER will aim is shown in Table 2. This list will be updated at each annual report (D7.3). Partners have well established contacts with some water agencies. We may consider inviting their representatives to joint training sessions.

Table 2. Water authority agencies to which eGROUNDWATER targets

NAME	AQUIFER MANAGED	LINKED CASE STUDY	COUNTRY	EXISTING CONTACT	CHANNEL	LANGUAGE	PARTNER(S) IN CHARGE
Confederación Hidrográfica del Júcar	90	Requena-Utiel	Spain	Yes	Phone, email, face-to-face	Spanish	UPV
Agência Portuguesa do Ambiente - Algarve	17	Campina de Faro	Portugal	Yes	Phone, email, face-to-face	Portuguese	UAlg
Sebou Catchment Management Agency	-	Ain Timguenay	Morocco	Yes	Phone, email, face-to-face	French	UMI
Souss Massa Catchment Management Agency	-	Ain Timguenay	Morocco	No	-	French	Cirad,UMI
Bouerrerreg Catchment Management Agency	-	Ain Timguenay	Morocco	No	-	French	Cirad,UMI
Confederación Hidrográfica del Segura	62	None	Spain	Yes	Phone, email	Spanish	UPV
Direção Regional de Agricultura e Pescas do Algarve (Direcção de Serviços de Desenvolvimento Agroalimentar e Rural)	-	Campina de Faro	Portugal	Yes	Phone, email, face-to-face	Portuguese	ISEG/ UALG
Nationale Hydraulic Resources Agency (ANRH)	-	Timimoun	Algeria	Yes	Phone, email, face-to-face	French	UADA - CIRAD
Foggara observatory	-	Timimoun	Algeria	Yes	Phone, email, face-to-face	French	UADA - CIRAD
Water Resources Department (DRE)	-	Timimoun	Algeria	Yes	Phone, face-to-face	French	UADA - CIRAD
Water Resources Integrated Management Agency (AGIRE)	-	Timimoun	Algeria	No	-	French	UADA - CIRAD
Saharan Hydrographic Basin Agency (ABH-S)	-	Timimoun	Algeria	Yes	-	French	UADA - CIRAD

2.3 Small farmer association and individual farmers

This target audience includes individual farmers and farmer associations with small number of members. Compared to large farmers associations, they do not have the capacity to play a significant influence on the aquifer abstractions by themselves. However, small farmers associations are very often older, more ingrained into the region and have a much higher potential to play a significant role for changing the governance schemes in the region. They are the majority in the Timimoun and Aim Tinguenay case studies, where currently collective associations regarding

groundwater management are limited. In Morocco, many small farmer associations take water from large aquifers such as the Saiss, Souss or Berrechid aquifers. In this situation, aquifer management cannot be done at the scale of each small farmer association. However, eGROUNDWATER aims at coordinating the small farmer associations by showing them the benefit of a common governance scheme supporter by the EIS.

The communication and dissemination objective for this audience is to show them how the EIS developed by eGROUNDWATER can assist them in achieving efficient and sustainable management practices. The differences between small or individual farmers associations and large farmers association are mainly:

- Small farmers associations and individual farmers are prone to suffer from lack of coordination due to the high number of stakeholders.
- Small farmers associations and individual farmers do not have the financial capacity of large associations.

For these reasons, the communication and dissemination activities should also show them how the EIS would facilitate coordination and collective action among them, as well as to provide a lean mechanism to improve their water use efficiency and productivity.

A list of small farmer associations or individual farmers at which eGROUNDWATER will aim is shown in Table 3. This list will be updated at each annual report (D7.3) with additional information, such as approximate size. Consortium partners are already in contact with relevant farmer associations in PRIMA regions. In the Requena-Utiel case study, individual associations have not been contacted yet, but communication with the central farmer association of the whole region has been established and they have started to contact individual farmer associations to talk about the project. We will invite their representatives to joint training sessions. Joint training sessions and workshops (Tasks 6.2 and 6.3) will help to demonstrate eGROUNDWATER potential to a variety of users.

Table 3. Individual farmers and small farmer associations

NAME	APPR. SIZE	AQUIFER	COUNTRY	EXISTING CONTACT	CHANNEL	LANGUAGE	PARTNER(S) IN CHARGE
C.R. El Rinconazo		Requena-Utiel	Spain	No/Partial	Email/face-to-face	Spanish	UPV
C.R. Boca Azul de Casas del Río		Requena-Utiel	Spain	No/Partial	Email/face-to-face	Spanish	UPV
C.R. Acequia San Blas		Requena-Utiel	Spain	No/Partial	Email/face-to-face	Spanish	UPV
C.R. Las Casas de Carcel		Requena-Utiel	Spain	No/Partial	Email/face-to-face	Spanish	UPV
C.R. de la Rinconada de Muñoz (Aldea de Casas del Río)		Requena-Utiel	Spain	No/Partial	Email/face-to-face	Spanish	UPV
C.R. El Pinar		Requena-Utiel	Spain	No/Partial	Email/face-to-face	Spanish	UPV
C.R. de la Vega		Requena-Utiel	Spain	No/Partial	Email/face-to-face	Spanish	UPV
C.R. de Albosa de Abajo		Requena-Utiel	Spain	No/Partial	Email/face-to-face	Spanish	UPV
C.R. Fuente de las Reinas		Requena-Utiel	Spain	No/Partial	Email/face-to-face	Spanish	UPV

C.R. Fuente del Pino		Requena-Utiel	Spain	No/Partial	Email/face-to-face	Spanish	UPV
C.R. Gollizno		Requena-Utiel	Spain	No/Partial	Email/face-to-face	Spanish	UPV
C.R. Riego Los Ruices		Requena-Utiel	Spain	No/Partial	Email/face-to-face	Spanish	UPV
C.R. Acequia del Judio del Pontón		Requena-Utiel	Spain	No/Partial	Email/face-to-face	Spanish	UPV
Grupo Sindical de Colonización nº 14.315		Requena-Utiel	Spain	No/Partial	Email/face-to-face	Spanish	UPV
C.R. Hermanos Fernández Abellám		Requena-Utiel	Spain	No/Partial	Email/face-to-face	Spanish	UPV
C.R. Pozo La Balsilla		Requena-Utiel	Spain	No/Partial	Email/face-to-face	Spanish	UPV
C.R. "Emilio Moya Latorre y Otros"		Requena-Utiel	Spain	No/Partial	Email/face-to-face	Spanish	UPV
C.U. "El Hontanar-Fase II"		Requena-Utiel	Spain	No/Partial	Email/face-to-face	Spanish	UPV
C.R. Los Pleitos		Requena-Utiel	Spain	No/Partial	Email/face-to-face	Spanish	UPV
C.R. "Las Carboneras"		Requena-Utiel	Spain	No/Partial	Email/face-to-face	Spanish	UPV
C.R. Pozo Cebadales		Requena-Utiel	Spain	No/Partial	Email/face-to-face	Spanish	UPV
C.R. Los Marcos		Requena-Utiel	Spain	No/Partial	Email/face-to-face	Spanish	UPV
Associação de regantes Sotavento		Beliche Dam	Portugal	Yes	email	Portuguese	ISEG/UALG
Associação de regantes de Silves, Lagoa e Portimão		Querança Silves	Portugal	Yes	Email, phone, face-to-face	Portuguese	ISEG/UALG
Local foggaras' associations		Timimoun	Algeria	No	-	Arabic	UADA-CIRAD
Local office of the National organization of environment and patrimony protection		Timimoun	Algeria	No	-	Arabic	UADA-CIRAD
Association of farmers of the Badriane perimeter		Timimoun	Algeria	No	-	Arabic/French	UADA-CIRAD

2.4 Drinking water sector

This target audience includes resident of the case studies, associations and public organizations responsible for drinking water management, treatment and/or supply. In some case studies, such as in the Algeria Timimoun aquifer, drinking water infrastructures are also use for familial farming.

NAME	AQUIFER	COUNTRY	EXISTING CONTACT	CHANNEL	LANGUAGE	PARTNER(S) IN CHARGE
Algérienne des eaux (ADE)	Timimoun	Algeria	Yes	E-mail, phone, face to face	French and Arabic	UA, Cirad

Direction des ressources en eau (DRE)	Timimoun	Algeria	Yes	E-mail, phone, face to face	French and Arabic	UA, Cirad
ANRH	Timimoun	Algeria	Yes	E-mail, phone, face to face	French and Arabic	UA, Cirad
Assemblée Populaire Communale (APC)	Timimoun	Algeria	Yes	E-mail, phone, face to face	Arabic	UA, Cirad
Association de quartier de l'oasis de Badriane de Timimoun	Timimoun	Algeria	Yes	E-mail, phone, face to face	Arabic	UA, Cirad

2.5 Tourism and golf sectors

This target audience includes tourism activities using groundwater (e.g. touristic residential areas, resorts, parks), as well as golf courses. Such users are quite important in Mediterranean economies, in particular in the northern coasts of the Mediterranean Sea and the southern coast of Portugal. This target audience has the following distinct features:

- They have a high financial capacity in terms of investments
- Although their water use is generally low compared to agricultural users (with the exception of golf courses), water quality plays a distinct role in their choice of location and supply source
- They are quite sensitive to the public perception regarding their use of water

This target audience is important in the Campina de Faro aquifer, which includes touristic areas and golf courses using groundwater.

The communication and dissemination objective for this audience is to show them the capabilities of the EIS on assessing and predicting water quality and achieving an efficient water use employing innovation technologies. Direct communication will be established with touristic activities in the Campina de Faro aquifer in order to involve them in the co-development of the EIS.

A list of groundwater users from the tourism and golf sectors at which eGROUNDWATER will aim is shown in Table 4. This list will be updated with relevant information at each annual report (D7.3). We may consider inviting their representatives to joint training sessions.

Table 4. Tourism and golf sector stakeholders to which eGROUNDWATER targets

NAME	AQUIFER	COUNTRY	EXISTING CONTACT	CHANNEL	LANGUAGE	PARTNER(S) IN CHARGE
Sociedade do golfe da quinta do lago SA	Campina de Faro	Portugal	Yes	email, phone, face-to-face	Portuguese	ISEG/UALG
Vale do Lobo	Campina de Faro	Portugal	Yes	Work in progress	English/Portuguese	ISEG/UALG

2.6 Scientific community

This target audience includes the scientific community in general, and more specifically, on water management, groundwater, agriculture, citizen science, and innovative information sources. The communication and dissemination objective for this audience is to present the capabilities of the

EIS on achieving efficient and sustainable groundwater management, in order to promote its use and find out pathways for its further development and application. Communication and dissemination towards this audience will be in line with the objectives depicted by the Exploitation Plan (D7.4) to be released at month 24. Dissemination and communication will be performed through scientific papers in research journals, articles posted in online blogs of strategic position, presentations in national and international congresses and forums, and in general in all the communication and dissemination means that can reach the scientific community. A brief collection of the scientific journals targeted by the consortium is presented in section 3.1.1.

2.7 General public

The communication and dissemination objective for this target audience will be the presentation of the capacities of the EIS, its functioning and its ability to support efficient and sustainable groundwater management, in order to increase its visibility and raise awareness of the challenges addressed by eGROUNDWATER. We will also aim at increasing the visibility of the PRIMA Foundation and programme to the public, as well the visibility of the eGROUNDWATER partners. Communication and dissemination to the general public will be made through the communication channels described in Section 3.

3 Communication and dissemination

3.1 Dissemination

3.1.1 Scientific Journals

eGROUNDWATER expects the publication of 12 scientific peer reviewed publications on the project's achievements in journals from Table 5. One of these correspond to Deliverable 2.2.

Open access will follow the Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020 and article 29.2 of the Grant Agreement (GA). The most relevant outputs will follow the Gold Open Access route to assure maximum impact of the project's results (approximately 4 papers). Article Processing Charges (APCs) for open-access publications have been considered and adequately included in the budget. The rest of the research papers will support Green Open Access, with embargo periods in line with the requirements of Article 29.2 of the GA. Electronic copies of published or final peer-reviewed manuscripts accepted for publication will be uploaded once available together with the corresponding underlying data to the institutional repository of the corresponding partner(s), the Zenodo public repository and/or the HAL repository (<https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/>).

Table 5. Candidate scientific journals selected for eGROUNDWATER's dissemination

NAME	ASSOCIATED RANKING	LANGUAGE	RANKING (POSITION)	OPEN ACCESS		OBSERVATIONS
				GREEN (emb.)	GOLD (APCs)	
Water Resources Research	JCR IF	English	4.309 (Q1)	Yes (6 months)	Yes (2.220 €)	Both green and gold open access comply with Art 29.2 of the GA

Journal of Hydrology	JCR IF	English	4.500 (Q1)	Yes (24 months)	Yes (2.840 €)	Green open access does not comply with Art 29.2 of the GA
Groundwater	JCR IF	English	2.205 (Q2)	Yes (12 months)	Yes (2.500 €)	Green open access does not comply with Art 29.2 of the GA
Hydrogeology journal	JCR IF	English	2.641 (Q2)	No	Yes (2570€)	
Hydrology and Earth System Sciences	JCR IF	English	5.153 (Q1)	No	Yes (77-93 €/page)	Open-access journal. Cost per page depends on the submission format (LaTeX, MS Word)
Environmental Science and Policy	SJR	English	1.82	Yes (24 months)	Yes (3.550\$)	Green open access does not comply with Art 29.2 of the GA
Environmental Modelling and Software	JCR IF	English	4.807 (Q1)	Yes (24 months)	Yes (2.750 €)	Green open access does not comply with Art 29.2 of the GA
Alternatives Rurales	No ranking	French	No	Open access	Yes	Open access journal
Water Alternatives	SJR	English	1.01	Open access	Yes	Ranked 55th out of 432 in the category Political Science in (Scopus-Elsevier)
Citizens Science: Theory and Practice	-	English	-	-	Yes (500GBP)	Open access journal
International Journal of the Commons (IJC)	JCR IF	English	1.423 (Q1)	No	Yes (870 €)	Open-access journal

3.1.2 Conferences

eGROUNDWATER expects to perform presentations in 8 conferences from the ones indicated in Table 6. The attendance, travelling and accommodation costs to these events have been adequately foreseen and indicated in the budget. Additional or alternative conferences may be targeted in case the COVID-19 health crisis disrupts the expected organization of the venues.

Table 6. Candidate conferences selected for eGROUNDWATER's dissemination

NAME	VENUE	FREQUENCY	ATTENDEES	TYPE OF AUDIENCE	LANGUAGE	SCOPE
European Geosciences Union General Assembly	Vienna (Austria)	Annual	15.000 – 20.000	Scientific	English	Worldwide
AGU Fall meeting	San Francisco – New Orleans – Chicago (USA)	Annual	30.000 – 40.000	Scientific	English	Worldwide
Associação Portuguesa dos Recursos Hídricos	Rotates	Annual	-	Scientific and professional	Portuguese	National
Earth System Governance	Rotates	Annual	-	Scientific	English	Worldwide
European Climate Change Adaptation conference	Rotates	Biannual	10.000 – 20.000	Scientific	English	Worldwide
Jornadas de Ingeniería del Agua	Rotates (Spain)	Biannual	500 – 1.000	Scientific and professional	Spanish	National
World Water Congress & Exhibition	Rotates	Biannual	-	Scientific and professional	English	Worldwide
World Water Forum	Rotates (Dakar)	Triennial	30.000 – 40.000	Scientific and professional	English	Worldwide

3.1.3 Workshops and meetings

eGROUNDWATER will organize its own workshops (Table 7) to communicate and disseminate the project and its results and in order to engage groundwater users, managers and other stakeholders in the collection of groundwater data; as well as to promote the EIS and the benefits brought by its use to all the target audiences indicated in Section 2. These workshops have been foreseen in the work plan and their cost has been adequately considered in the budget.

The COVID-19 disruption for travelling and organizing in-person meetings has been taken into account, as reflected in D1.2 Quality and Risk Management Plan. Remote meetings and non-face-to-face encounters will be applied for all planned meetings and workshops if required. The information provided by the World Health Organization and all national health authorities in charge of the territories involved in the workshops will be regularly reviewed by the PC and the workshops organizers.

Table 7. List of planned workshops organized during eGROUNDWATER

TASK	NAME	EXPECTED DATE	ORGANIZER	VENUE	EXPECTED ATTENDEES	LANGUAGE	EXPECTED COST
3.1	Introductory workshop	Nov-2020	CIRAD-UADA	Adrar (Algeria)			
3.1	Introductory workshop	Nov-2020	BRGM-UMI-CIRAD	Meknès (Morocco)			
3.1	Introductory workshop	Nov-2020	ISEG-UAlg	Faro (Portugal)	UAlg	English/Portuguese	
3.1	Introductory workshop	Nov-2020	UPV	Utiel (Spain)	UPV	Spanish	
3.2	Co-design of EIS (1)	Feb-2021	CIRAD-UADA	Adrar (Algeria)			
3.2	Co-design of EIS (1)	Feb-2021	BRGM-UMI-CIRAD	Meknès (Morocco)			
3.2	Co-design of EIS (1)	Feb-2021	ISEG-UAlg	Faro (Portugal)	UAlg	English/Portuguese	
3.2	Co-design of EIS (1)	Feb-2021	UPV	Utiel (Spain)		Spanish	
3.2	Co-design of EIS (2)	May-2021	CIRAD-UADA	Adrar (Algeria)	UAlg	English/Portuguese	1700
3.2	Co-design of EIS (2)	May-2021	BRGM-UMI-CIRAD	Meknès (Morocco)	UAlg	English/Portuguese	1700
3.2	Co-design of EIS (2)	May-2021	ISEG-UAlg	Faro (Portugal)	UAlg	English/Portuguese	
3.2	Co-design of EIS (2)	May-2021	UPV	Utiel (Spain)	UAlg	Spanish	
5.3	Co-design of improved management using the EIS	Feb-2023	CIRAD-UADA	Adrar (Algeria)			
5.3	Co-design of improved management using the EIS	Feb-2023	BRGM-UMI-CIRAD	Meknès (Morocco)			
5.3	Co-design of improved management using the EIS	Feb-2023	ISEG-UAlg	Faro (Portugal)	UAlg	English/Portuguese	
5.3	Co-design of improved management using the EIS	Feb-2023	UPV	Utiel (Spain)	UPV	Spanish	
6.4	Co-creation of scenarios for new groundwater management frameworks	Jun-2023	CIRAD-UADA	Adrar (Algeria)	UAlg	English/Portuguese	1700
6.4	Co-creation of scenarios for new groundwater management frameworks	Jun-2023	BRGM-UMI-CIRAD	Meknès (Morocco)	UAlg	English/Portuguese	1700
6.4	Co-creation of scenarios for new groundwater management frameworks	Jun-2023	ISEG-UAlg	Faro (Portugal)	UAlg	English/Portuguese	
6.4	Co-creation of scenarios for new groundwater management frameworks	Jun-2023	UPV	Valencia (Spain)	UPV/BRGM	Spanish	
5.4	Final case study workshop on improving groundwater management	Sep-2023	CIRAD-UADA	Adrar (Algeria)			

5.4	Final case study workshop on improving groundwater management	Sep-2023	BRGM-UMI-CIRAD	Meknès (Morocco)			
5.4	Final case study workshop on improving groundwater management	Sep-2023	ISEG-UAlg	Faro (Portugal)	UAlg	English/Portuguese	
5.4	Final case study workshop on improving groundwater management	Sep-2023	UPV	Utiel (Spain)	UPV	Spanish	
6.4	Implementation issues for an improved groundwater management framework	Oct-2023	CIRAD-UADA	Adrar (Algeria)			
6.4	Implementation issues for an improved groundwater management framework	Oct-2023	BRGM-UMI-CIRAD	Meknès (Morocco)			
6.4	Implementation issues for an improved groundwater management framework	Oct-2023	ISEG-UAlg	Faro (Portugal)	UAlg	English/Portuguese	
6.4	Implementation issues for an improved groundwater management framework	Oct-2023	UPV	Valencia (Spain)	UPV	Spanish	
6.2	Training program evaluation	Nov-2023	BRGM	Meknès (Morocco)			
6.2	Training program evaluation	Nov-2023	BRGM	Montpellier (France)			
5.4 – 6.1	Final workshop on improving groundwater management with all case studies	Dec-2023	UPV	Valencia (Spain)	UAlg	English	787

Furthermore, eGROUNDWATER will participate in workshops not directly organized in the frame of the project to disseminate and communicate its results (Table 8). The costs associated with attending these workshops have also been adequately considered in the budget.

Table 8. Other workshops selected for dissemination

NAME	EXPECTED DATE	ORGANIZER	VENUE	EXPETED ATTENDEES	LANGUAGE
Training session about Agent-Based Modelling (ABM) for GW resources management	Oct-2021	CIRAD-UADA	Adrar-Algeria	Master and PHD Students and Academics from UADA Engineers from technical services	French
Training workshops based on sharing experience of the Algerian case study	Fev-2023	CIRAD	Algeria- France	Academics and professionals of GW management	English – French

3.2 Communication

3.2.1 Online communication

eGROUNDWATER will build a strong online presence to attract target audiences to the project. The online communication strategy of the project will have three sides:

Webpages

The project website (egroundwater.com) has been developed for collecting the main results and communicating the project's achievements during the project duration. The website is developed in English, with additional translations to French, Portuguese and Spanish.

The website is designed and maintained by VitaminaEstudio, a Spanish based communication and marketing company specialized in developing corporate and project websites. Resources for

subcontracting the website development were already allocated in the GA (Section 4.2). The subcontracted company uses the Wordpress technology and its multiple modules to create modular and easily expandable websites. The website will describe the project inception, goals, methodology and the involved consortium members. Additionally, it will have a section dedicated to the different case studies where users will be informed of the unique features and characteristics of each hub of the project. A section of the webpage will be used for sharing the publicly available project deliverables, with links for downloading the files in PDF format.

The subcontracted company has also developed the visual identity of the project, including the vector-based logo of the project in different shapes and chromatic formats (Figure 1).

Figure 1. eGROUNDWATER logo in two different formats

Links to other communication platforms, such as the project’s Twitter account and the PRIMA foundation website are included into the website as well. A subscription form for receiving the eGROUNDWATER newsletter will also be included.

The webpage will have a blog section with frequent publications about:

- Short news about the progress of the project, including the organization of events, workshop, and general meetings.
- Publication of relevant results achieved by the project.
- News related to groundwater management.

The publications will be supported dedicated and stock pictures. Relevant content will be available for download by relying on optimized photographic for the web, and all deliveries will be download (pdf format).

Furthermore, eGROUNDWATER’s partners will use the following webpages from their organizations to communicate eGROUNDWATER projects and achievements.

Table 9. List of webpages used by the partners for communication

URL	RELATED PARTNER	LANGUAGE	TARGET AUDIENCE
https://www.iiama.upv.es/iiama/es/	UPV	Spanish / English	Water resource stakeholders Academic community
https://www.ualg.pt/pt/content/projetos-investigacao	UALg	Portuguese/ English	Water resource stakeholders Academic community Civil society
https://csg.rc.iseg.ulisboa.pt/projecto-egroundwater/	ISEG	Portuguese/ English	Water resource stakeholders Academic community

https://www.g-eau.fr/index.php/fr/recherche/projets-en-cours	Cirad and INRAE	French/English	Water resource stakeholders Academic community
https://www.univ-adrar.edu.dz/	UADA	Arabic/Frensh/English	Water resource stakeholders Academic community

Social networks

eGROUNDWATER's partners will use the following social network accounts from their organizations to communicate eGROUNDWATER projects and achievements.

Table 10. List of social network accounts used by the partners for communication

SOCIAL NETWORK	ACCOUNT	RELATED PARTNER	LANGUAGE	FOLLOWERS
Twitter	@iiama_upv	UPV	Spanish	4,559
Facebook	@iiama.upv	UPV	Spanish	1,840
Twitter	@UAlg	UAlg	Portuguese	9.300
Facebook	@universidade.algarve	UAlg	Portuguese	46.190
Instagram	@ualg_universidadedoalgarve	UAlg	Portuguese	9.800
Youtube	https://www.youtube.com/user/universidadealgarve	UAlg	Portuguese English	11.200
Facebook	@univeadrar	UADA	French	12,699

A twitter account for eGROUNDWATER has been created for dissemination and communication (@egroundwater2). The account will be managed by a community manager assigned by the subcontracted communication agency. The twitter account will update the public on the project's achievements and will announce key events or milestones such as workshops, scientific publications and other relevant news. The account will be a channel for sharing and exchanging news between researchers.

The expected content of the publications will be:

- Blog content.
- Project news (workshop, meetings, milestones).
- Relevant content of project members.
- Industry news.
- Retweets of project partners.
- Technician and farmer interviews.
- Retweets of interesting external content.

The project will be connected to all the PRIMA's channels on social media to maximize the reach of the project's publications.

Newsletters

Electronic newsletters reporting on project events and results will be issued on the project's website reaching a wide community of potential stakeholders.

eGW will get contacts and subscriptions of the newsletter through a web application form. Newsletter subscribers and partners contacts will create a database and will be used for dissemination of information.

Different types of Newsletter that will send by eGW:

- Monthly Newsletter with a news summary, post and events/milestone.
- Specific Newsletter of each one of the meetings of study cases.
- Occasionally, any Newsletter that will consider necessary.

3.2.2 Traditional media

Pictures of all case studies will be taken to illustrate the webpage of the project and to be shared through social media. In the Requena-Utiel case study, a short video (2-3 minutes) will be filmed, edited and released by the communication and marketing company subcontracted. The video will collect 'in situ' interviews with farmers and technician of the region, and will illustrate the stakeholders' point of view about the project and the groundwater issue tackled in the region.

Mass media presence (TV, newspapers, magazines and radio). Press notes about the project will be developed whenever relevant events and activities take place. The press notes will be designed by the Communication and Dissemination Unit, translated and distributed by all partners through their networks.

Posters will be designed for presenting the project in conferences, workshops and exhibitions, describing the work in progress to the target audience. All posters will contain the PRIMA foundation logo and all relevant information to acknowledge the founding institutions involved into the project.

4 The Communication and Dissemination unit

The Communication & Dissemination Unit (CDU) will coordinate communication activities considering the linguistic and socio-cultural background of all PRIMA countries involved into the project. The CDU will be led by UPV through the PC, Prof. Manuel Pulido-Velazquez. The UPV communication team involved into the project has long-term experience and has won national-scale awards by their communication activities. The CDU will comprise 4 additional members, one per each country represented in the consortium Algeria (Dr. Salem Idda), France (Dr. Jean-Daniel Rinaudo), Morocco (Dr. Zhour Bouzidi), Portugal (Dr. Marta Varanda). The CDU will be responsible for monitoring and implementing the planned communication and dissemination activities, following the actions described in this document and establishing corrective actions if required.